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Exploring Hybrid Quantum-Classical Algorithms: Theory, Implementation and Optimization Techniques

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Abstract

This paper explores hybrid quantum-classical algorithms in the context of variational quantum algorithms, focusing on the Variational Quantum Eigensolver and the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA). It investigates their theoretical foundations, discusses key elements, implementation strategies, and performance optimization techniques within the PennyLane framework. The QAOA is implemented with various optimization levels, circuit depths, and Ansätze. Experimental results on the MaxCut and Traveling Salesman problems demonstrate how these algorithms perform under different configurations, providing insights into practical applications to pave the way towards the quantum utility era.

1 Introduction

In the book *Quantum Generations* [5], Kragh offers an insight from some late nineteenth century physicists’ perspective that some argued the fundamental principles in their respective fields were already uncovered, and what is left is to fill in minor details. This notion serves as a reminder that today’s theoretical challenges will become tomorrow’s practical requirements. Classical computers and algorithms face exponential scaling hurdles

when tackling NP-complete problems in mathematics, chemistry and other fields. Although Quantum advantage has been achieved in very special cases of optimization problems [1]. The main constraint to move forward lies in the hardware. Large-scale and reliable quantum devices are still required to run even naive-quantum algorithms, falling short of their full potential, and are hard to implement due to limited electron fidelity, coherence problems, and constraints on circuit topologies. Foundational work by McClean et al. [7] introduced the use of parameterized quantum circuits, where candidate quantum states are prepared and iteratively optimized by classical computers to minimize a problem-specific cost function. This approach not only extracts value from today’s Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) devices by combining classical optimization and well-researched machine learning areas but also tames the concerns that quantum software development only helps us to put the cart before the horse, showing it can drive progress through uncovering near-term practical applications. This paper explores the theoretical foundations of the Variational Quantum Algorithms (VQAs), details the implementation of the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) and presents benchmarking results to solve combinatorial optimization problems.

2 Background

2.1 Hamiltonian Formulation

In quantum mechanics, the Hamiltonian is an operator that represents the system energy and is governed by the time evolution described by the time-dependent Schrödinger equation (1)

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\Psi(t)\rangle = \hat{H} |\Psi(t)\rangle, \quad (1)$$

the quantum state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ evolves unitarily under the system Hamiltonian \hat{H} . For time-independent \hat{H} , the evolution simplifies to (2)

$$|\Psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar} |\Psi(0)\rangle, \quad (2)$$

This allows us to construct a parameterized quantum state $|\Psi(\theta)\rangle$ to approximate the ground state of a cost Hamiltonian \hat{H}_C , which encodes the problem of interest—such as molecular energy or combinatorial objectives by weighted sum of observables (3), i.e., Hermitian operators representing measurable quantities \hat{O}_k .

$$\hat{H}_C = \sum_k c_k \hat{O}_k, \quad (3)$$

The goal is to minimize the expectation value (4) using classical optimization over the parameters θ . The minimum of this expression corresponds to the ground state energy of \hat{H}_C , ideally yielding a solution to the original problem.

$$\langle \hat{H}_C \rangle = \langle \Psi(\theta) | \hat{H}_C | \Psi(\theta) \rangle. \quad (4)$$

2.2 Ansatz

The Hilbert space of a quantum system encompasses all possible quantum states the system can be in. The space dimensionality is exponential, for a system of n qubits, there are 2^n dimensions. To navigate in this complexity, quantum circuits known as *Ansätze* are used to define structured subspaces, since “one does not simply walk

into” Hilbert space¹. An Ansatz is a quantum circuit structure that introduces interference patterns through entanglement.

This circuit prepares a correlated state and encodes a simple relation:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(|00\rangle + \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |10\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |11\rangle \right)$$

where the rotation angle θ acts as a tunable constant offset. It “tilts” the solution space away from pure Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle$ and allows for asymmetric correlation that can be formulated as

$$x = y + c \pmod{2}$$

then the Hilbert space is effectively constrained to favor the solution subspace.

Optimizable Ansatz

In VQAs, a parametrized *Ansatz* (5) defines the trial wavefunction to explore the candidate solution subspace.

$$|\Psi(\theta)\rangle = U(\theta) |0\rangle^{\otimes n}. \quad (5)$$

There is no trivial Ansatz structure, the design of this circuit interests this main trade-off: its *expressibility*, or the breadth of quantum states it can represent, and its *trainability*, or the ease with which it can be optimized. As an Ansatz becomes more complicated, it becomes hard to train since it contains more parameters to optimize.

Ansätze generally fall into two categories:

¹A reference to Boromir’s line in *The Fellowship of the Ring*—a reference to the difficulty of navigating vast, uncharted spaces.

- **Hardware-efficient Ansätze** consist of shallow layers of parameterized single-qubit rotations and native entangling gates. While more noise-resilient, their generic structure often fails to capture problem-specific correlations, limiting solution quality.

A basic form for n qubits is:

$$U(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \left(\bigotimes_{j=1}^n R_Y(\theta_j) \right) \cdot \text{EntanglingLayer}$$

- **Problem-tailored Ansätze** exploit particle symmetries in quantum chemistry or constraints in combinatorial optimization. Typically they exhibit richer entanglement patterns with greater expressibility, allowing them to better approximate complex ground states:

$$U(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \left(\prod_{(i,j) \in E} e^{-i\theta_{ij} Z_i Z_j} \right) \cdot \left(\bigotimes_{k=1}^n R_X(\beta_k) \right)$$

This encodes edge-wise correlations through ZZ interactions, guiding the circuit toward low-cost configurations on the problem graph.

Ultimately, the challenge in Ansatz design is to strike a balance between expressibility and trainability. A highly expressive Ansatz increases the chance of capturing the true ground state, but may become prohibitively hard to optimize or encounter barren plateaus. Simpler circuits are easier to train but may overlook important regions of the solution space. This trade-off remains a central design question in the development of scalable and effective VQAs.

2.3 Gradients in Quantum Circuits

Gradient-based optimization of quantum circuits in variational algorithms requires computing the derivatives of expectation values of observables with respect to the circuit parameters. For gates of the form: $e^{-i\theta G}$, where G is typically a Pauli operator, the *parameter-shift rule* [3] provides a hardware-friendly method for computing the gradients (6).

It requires only two evaluations of the circuit with shifted parameters:

$$\frac{\partial C(\theta)}{\partial \theta} = \frac{1}{2} \left[C\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) - C\left(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right], \quad (6)$$

This approach is the same for many common quantum gates and is used in current optimizations due to its practical implementation on real quantum hardware.

3 Variational Quantum Algorithms

This section introduces VQAs, which combine problem Hamiltonians and parameterized Ansätze into a hybrid quantum-classical framework that optimizes circuit parameters to approximate ground state energies or minimize cost functions.

3.1 Variational Quantum Eigensolver

The Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) [8] is based on the variational principle, which guarantees that for any normalized quantum state $|\psi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\rangle$ prepared by an Ansatz, the expectation value of the Hamiltonian \hat{H} satisfies (7), where E_0 is the true ground state energy, and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are the tunable parameters of the Ansatz.

$$E_0 \leq \langle \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) | \hat{H} | \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \rangle. \quad (7)$$

How VQE Works

1. A parameterized quantum circuit (Ansatz) is used to prepare an initial state $|\psi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\rangle$.
2. The expectation value $\langle \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) | \hat{H} | \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \rangle$ is then estimated by measuring the Hamiltonian's terms via multiple sampling.
3. A classical optimizer adjusts the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ to minimize the measured energy.
4. Steps 1–3 are repeated until convergence to an approximate ground state energy.

Application in Quantum Chemistry

In quantum chemistry, the time-independent Schrödinger equation (8) governs the molecular electronic structure. Classical methods such as Hartree-Fock [10] approximate the wavefunction by assuming independent electrons in an average potential.

$$\hat{H}|\psi\rangle = E|\psi\rangle. \quad (8)$$

This rough method neglects inter-electron interactions arising from Coulomb repulsion and quantum uncertainty. Thus, even in the lowest-energy configuration, electrons avoid fixed positions, dynamically adjusting through entanglement and superposition. The VQE captures these many body effects using parameterized quantum circuits, yielding more accurate ground-state energies.

3.2 Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm

3.2.1 Adiabatic Inspiration for QAOA

QAOA is motivated by adiabatic quantum evolution [4]. The term “adiabatic” comes from the Greek “ἀ-διὰβαίνω” (*a-diabainō*), meaning “not crossable,” referring to transitions between energy levels—local minima. Ideally, a quantum system initialized in the ground state of a simple Hamiltonian \hat{H}_M remains in the ground state as it slowly evolves toward a problem Hamiltonian \hat{H}_C . Rather than exploring the solution space via a fixed cost function, QAOA interpolates the cost Hamiltonian \hat{H}_C during this evolution to guide the system toward the optimal solution.

However, continuous adiabatic evolution is difficult to realize. Analog annealers follow a fixed evolution path that is hard to analyze and very sensitive to problem encoding [11].

3.2.2 Discretizing Adiabatic Evolution

QAOA discretizes and approximates the adiabatic evolution using alternating unitaries based on the mixer and cost Hamiltonians. Since \hat{H}_M and \hat{H}_C

Figure 1: Energy Landscape Change in Time during Adiabatic Evolution

generally do not commute, their combined evolution cannot be captured by a single exponential. Instead, it uses a first-order Trotter-Suzuki decomposition [9] to approximate the time-dependent Hamiltonian (9) with a product of unitaries, as expressed in (10).

$$\hat{H}(t) = (1 - s(t))\hat{H}_M + s(t)\hat{H}_C, \quad (9)$$

$$e^{-i(\hat{H}_C + \hat{H}_M)t} \approx \left(e^{-i\gamma\hat{H}_C} e^{-i\beta\hat{H}_M} \right)^p. \quad (10)$$

This decomposition allows the evolution under non-commuting Hamiltonians to be implemented on gate-based quantum hardware. Non-commutativity introduces approximation errors, but increasing the number of layers p improves the fidelity of the overall evolution.

Figure 2: Decomposition of Adiabatic Hamiltonian
Source: PennyLane Codebook

3.2.3 QAOA Ansatz and Optimization

The QAOA state after p layers is given by (11), where $\vec{\gamma}$ and $\vec{\beta}$ are variational parameters optimized classically to minimize the cost Hamiltonian (12).

$$|\Psi(\vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta})\rangle = \prod_{l=1}^p e^{-i\beta_l \hat{H}_M} e^{-i\gamma_l \hat{H}_C} |+\rangle^{\otimes n}, \quad (11)$$

$$\langle \hat{H}_C \rangle = \langle \Psi | \hat{H}_C | \Psi \rangle. \quad (12)$$

3.2.4 Suitability for Graph-Based Problems

The QAOA is particularly well suited for combinatorial optimization problems that can be expressed as Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) or Ising models. These include many graph-structured problems that map QUBO penalty matrices to Ising Hamiltonians:

- **MaxCut:** Partitioning nodes of a graph to maximize the number of edges crossing the cut, using pairwise $Z_i Z_j$ interactions.
- **Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP):** Encoding the tour as binary variables $x_{i,t}$ indicating whether city i is visited at step t , with distance costs and constraint penalties.

The locality of interactions, namely the edges in these problems, can be easily translated to two-qubit gates in the QAOA circuit, making the algorithm efficient and scalable for such tasks.

How QAOA Works

1. A parameterized quantum circuit (Ansatz) is constructed using p layers of alternating cost and mixer Hamiltonians.
2. The circuit prepares a trial state $|\Psi(\vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta})\rangle$ from the initial superposition $|+\rangle^{\otimes n}$ or best classical approximation—warm-start.
3. The expectation value $\langle \hat{H}_C \rangle$ is estimated via repeated measurements.
4. A classical optimizer updates $\vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta}$ to minimize the cost.
5. Steps 1–4 are repeated until convergence to an approximate solution.

4 Experiments

This section aims to analyze how the various components of the procedure influence its overall effectiveness, with a particular focus on their impact on experimental performance, convergence behavior, and solution quality.

4.1 Benchmarking Problems

- **Weighted MaxCut:** Random weighted graphs with 10 nodes and edge probabilities in the range 0.4–0.6:

$$\hat{H}_C = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{1 - Z_i Z_j}{2}.$$

- **Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP):** Formulated as a QUBO, 3 cities 9 qubits, using a penalty parameter $\lambda = 100$ to enforce constraint satisfaction. The cost Hamiltonian is derived from the QUBO matrix Q :

$$\hat{H}_C = \sum_{i,j} Q_{ij} Z_i Z_j,$$

where Q encodes the distance-based cost and permutation constraints for valid TSP tours. The Ansatz for TSP uses a `ring_XY` mixer to promote exploration while preserving the tour constraints.

4.2 Setup

- **Software:** Python 3.10.12, CUDA 12, PennyLane 0.41.1, JAX 0.4.28, Optax 0.2.5. All benchmarking code for QAOA experiments is available and reproducible [2].
- **Hardware:** Intel Core Ultra 195H (22 cores), 32 GB RAM, NVIDIA RTX 4070 Mobile GPU (8 GB VRAM). The benchmark was created under WSL, the actual allocated memory is limited to 15 GB.
- **Monitoring Tools:** GPU utilization was tracked via `GPUtil`, while CPU and RAM usage were monitored using `psutil` with a 0.5-second sampling interval.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 QAOA Convergence Analysis

This experiment investigates the evolution of amplitude and phase parameters that determine the rotation angles in the QAOA Ansatz that are essential for steering the state toward optimal solutions. By tuning these parameters, we control the convergence dynamics and the final solution distribution under different Trotterization depths. This visualization helps to understand how the cost and mixer Hamiltonians work together to approximate optimal solutions.

In Fig. 3 below, it is observed that a warm-started QAOA applied to a MaxCut instance successfully converged to one of the optimal solutions through exploration. The jumps in the phase axis show how the mixer helps escape from potential local minima and explores the Hilbert space in a structured manner.

Figure 3: Amplitude and phase distribution of a warm-started QAOA solution instance.

The cost function in Fig. 4 drops rapidly in early iterations, indicating that warm-started, shallow QAOA circuits can converge quickly. Interestingly, a key distinction emerges between QAOA and classical learning algorithms: quantum convergence behavior does not exhibit overfitting. While

deeper circuits introduce more parameters and longer training, performance does not degrade due to "memorization"; rather, it tends to plateau during training—a phenomenon known as the *barren plateau* [6] problem, reflecting the algorithm’s physical constraints rather than data generalization limits.

Figure 4: Training dynamics of QAOA: Cost function evolution over optimization epochs.

5.2 Identifying and Characterizing Optimal Solutions in QAOA

This experiment evaluates how an optimal QAOA circuit explores valid solutions in a TSP instance while preserving the one-hot encoding enforced by a problem-specific ring-XY mixer.

Figure 5: Top bitstring probability changes in a warm-started 3-city TSP.

As shown in Fig. 5, the red bars indicate the initial amplitudes, warm-started to a suboptimal state. By the final layer (blue bars), the probability mass spreads across multiple solutions of similar cost, reflecting the symmetry inherent to the problem. This experiment demonstrates QAOA’s ability to sample from a degenerate solution space while respecting structural constraints.

5.3 Effect of Mixer Types and Depth Values in QAOA

This experiment analyzes how the choice of mixer (X or XY) and circuit depth influences convergence and solution quality in MaxCut problems.

Figure 6: QAOA performance on MaxCut with different mixer types and circuit depths. The middle configuration yields the optimal result.

As shown in Fig. 6, where each polar plot’s angle reflects mixer-induced rotation while distance from the center represents cut quality—farther points indicate better solutions—this illustrates how mixer type and depth affect exploration and performance. Shallow X-mixer circuits converge quickly but often to suboptimal cuts. Deeper XY-mixer circuits explore more but converge slowly and unstably. The best results come from moderately deep X-mixer circuits (middle plot), balancing stability and exploration.

5.4 Optimization Strategy and Execution Backend

This experiment explores the effect of JAX-based optimization.

Table 1: Effect of JAX on per-epoch and total execution time (in seconds) for 4 training epochs.

	Ep. 0	Ep. 1	Ep. 2	Ep. 3	Total
JAX	4.79	0.01	0.01	0.01	4.84
Default	1.74	1.75	1.74	1.84	7.07

As shown in Table 1, JAX introduces initial overhead due to just-in-time (JIT) compilation, but drastically reduces runtime in subsequent epochs—resulting in faster total execution.

5.5 Experimental Limitations

Problem sizes were limited by memory and backend constraints under a WSL-based laptop environment. MaxCut experiments were restricted to weighted graphs with up to 12 nodes/qubits, and TSP instances were limited to 3 cities (9 qubits). CPU-backend device simulations hit memory limits at 15 qubits, while GPU backends were able to handle 22 qubits at most. However, due to prohibitive simulation times, experiments were performed in the 9–12 qubit range to ensure timely and presentable results.

6 Conclusion

This work evaluated hybrid quantum-classical optimization strategies, providing theoretical background and explaining what happens under the hood before applying them through the lens of QAOA. Despite the hardware limitations, the experiments—supported by the theoretical part of the paper—demonstrated that efficient VQA implementations are feasible and effective using current high-performance tools such as PennyLane, JAX, and GPU acceleration. The promising applications demonstrated here prove that, with the growing power of the quantum world and modern machine learning ecosystems, hybrid quantum algorithms are becoming practical for real-world tasks from route optimization and job scheduling to drug discovery, protein folding and discovering new materials that we have yet to even dream of.

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